

Reaction of Organohalogens with *in situ* Electrogenerated Superoxide Ion

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Superoxide ion, generated by electrochemical reduction of O₂ in dimethylformamide at mercury cathode, reacts as an effective nucleophile with haloarenes (1a-4a) and as a base with phenacyl halides (5a and 6a) affording phenols (1a-4b) and *trans*-dibenzoyl ethene (5b) respectively.

Superoxide ion is not only one of the most important activated forms of molecular oxygen in biological systems¹⁻³ but also possess various reactivities⁴, viz. characteristics of a base, nucleophile, oxidant, reductant, free radical and an electron transfer agent. The use of superoxide as alkali metal salts in organic reaction has not been fruitful owing to the lack of solubility of these salts in organic solvents⁵. On the other hand, the electrochemical method is more convenient because superoxide ion is continuously generated on the electrode and its solubility is sufficiently high in presence of the tetrabutylammonium cation of the supporting electrolyte⁶.

In continuation of our investigation⁷ about the reactivity of electrogenerated superoxide ion, we reported recently the efficient regeneration of phenols from the corresponding tosylates⁸ in which superoxide ion acts as a nucleophilic reagent and performs the act in an addition-elimination process. Recently, the reactivity of superoxide ion as a nucleophile and a base has been reported for cyclisation⁹ and for inducing Favorskii rearrangements¹⁰ of some suitable organohalogen substrates. In the present paper we provide yet another example of the dual reactivity of electrogenerated superoxide anion as an effective nucleophile and as a base towards haloarenes and phenacyl halides respectively affording phenols and *trans*-dibenzoyl ethene in good yield.

Results and Discussion

The formation of phenols from aryl halides indicates that superoxide ion behaves as an effective nucleophile and it replaces halogen in an addition-elimination process similar to the one already reported by our group⁸.

In the reaction of phenacyl halide and superoxide ion, the latter behaves as an effective base and seems to deprotonate active methylene proton of phenacyl halide to give rise to a carbanion intermediate which, after elimination of halide ion affords *trans*-dibenzoyl ethene via a carbene intermediate route (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

While there are many examples in the literature of superoxide ion acting as a base, the reaction of phenacyl halides (**5a**, **6a**) reported in the present study is novel.

Typical cyclic voltammogram of phenacyl chloride (**5a**) is shown in Fig. 1. Similar voltammograms were obtained with other compounds also. Fig. 1 reveals that molecular oxygen is

Fig 1 Cyclic voltammogram of phenacyl chloride (**5a**) . (---) in presence of oxygen saturation, (.....) in absence of oxygen and (—) cyclic voltammogram of oxygen reduction. electrolyte 0.1 M TBAP/DMSO, electrode, Pt, scan rate, 200 mV s⁻¹.

reduced to superoxide ion at -985 mV and this species is reoxidised in the reverse sweep of potential at -480 mV. The ratio of anodic to cathodic peak current is approximately unity which indicates that oxygen reduction is single electron process, and also reveals that superoxide ion formed during the cathodic sweep does not react but can all be reoxidised when the potential sweep is reversed. Under nitrogen atmosphere, **5a** is reduced at -1740 mV. On the other hand, in the reduction of **5a** in presence of oxygen, the cathodic peak current is increased and slight anodic shift in peak potential is observed. Whereas the anodic peak of the O₂⁻/O₂ couple corresponding to the process, O₂⁻ → O₂ + e⁻, disappears indicating that there is fast subsequent chemical reaction between O₂⁻ and substrate affecting the product formation.

Experimental

Haloarenes (**1a-4a**) and phenacyl halides (**5a** and **6a**) are prepared according to the procedures¹¹, and characterised on the basis of their physical and spectral data. They were subjected to the reaction with superoxide ion to yield products **1b-4b** and **5b** respectively. All the products obtained were fully characterised by usual methods.

Melting points were measured with a Buchi apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (90 MHz) on a Jeol FX-900 FT-NMR spectrometer. The quantity of electricity passed was measured using a copper coulometer. DMF was used after drying over molecular sieves (3Å). Oxygen was dried by passing through a packed column of anhydrous CaSO₄, sodium hydroxide pellets and molecular sieves (3Å). Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with an X-Y (t) recorder (Servogor 733). All measurements were carried out at 25° using a three-electrode system consisting of a counter (stationary platinum disc; 22 mm in diameter), a platinum rod test electrode, 0.1 M TBAP (tetrabutylammonium perchlorate) in DMSO (spectroscopic grade) served as supporting electrolyte. The scan rate of potential was 200 mV s⁻¹.

The electrochemical cell consisted of a double-walled glass cell (capacity 150 ml) in which a medium porosity glass frit separated the anodic and cathodic chambers. The mercury pool (23.76 cm²) and platinum foil (3.78 cm²) served as an anode and a cathode respectively. Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) served as a reference electrode. The teflon cover at the head of the electrolytic cell contained holes for connecting mercury pool and for passing nitrogen or oxygen gas. Agitation of the catholyte was achieved using small magnetic bar and through bubbling of oxygen.

In a typical experiment, the cathodic chamber containing the electrolyte (50 ml) was purged with nitrogen for 15 min. The electrolyte solution was first pre-electrolysed at -1.9 V vs SCE

TABLE 1—CONTROLLED POTENTIAL MACRO-ELECTROLYSIS OF OXYGEN IN THE PRESENCE OF ORGANOHALOGENS

Substrate (1a-6a)	Product (1b-5b)	Current(mA)		Electricity passed Coulomb	Current efficiency %	Reaction period h	Product yield %
		Initial	Final				
Benzyl chloride	Benzyl alcohol	150	15	868	99	10	70 ^a
<i>o</i> -Bromotoluene	<i>o</i> -Cresol	175	12	1158	40	08	60
<i>o</i> -Iodobenzoic acid	Salicylic acid	190	15	617	56	12	68
1-Bromonaphthalene	1-Naphthol	180	08	810	60	10	70
Phenacyl chloride	Dibenzoyl ethene	250	30	289	78	12	80
Phenacyl bromide	Dibenzoyl ethene	240	25	361	69	15	85

^aTrace amount of benzoic acid was also detected.

until the background current dropped to about 2 mA. Cyclohexene (2 ml) was added in the anodic chamber to absorb the liberated bromine (cyclohexene is not needed when tetrabutylammonium perchlorate was used as a supporting electrolyte). Catholyte was saturated with oxygen for 30 min. Phenacyl chloride (**5a**; 0.5 g, 3.24 mmol) was then added to cathodic chamber. Oxygen was bubbled through the solution during period of electrolysis carried out at constant potential of -1.0 V vs SCE. The current decreased from an initial 250 to 30 mA. Completion was checked by tlc and current did fall appreciably (Table 1). After completion of the reaction, catholyte was taken into cold water (100 ml) and extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml). The extract was dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄), filtered and the solvent removed on a rotatory evaporator to yield *trans*-dibenzoyl ethene (**5b**) which was recrystallised from ethanol (0.61 g, 80%), m.p. 110°; ν_{\max} 1687 (CO).

For isolation of products **1a-4a** the following work-up procedure was adopted. The catholyte was poured in 10% aqueous NaHCO₃ solution (150 ml) and extracted with methylene chloride (2 × 25 ml). The aqueous layer was dried under reduced pressure to remove DMF. The resulting solid was dissolved in water (25 ml) and acidified with 5% aqueous HCl (20 ml). The precipitated phenols (**1a-4a**) were extracted with ether, purified by Kugelrohr distillation/recrystallisation and identified by comparing their b.p./m.p. and spectral data (ir and pmr) with

those of authentic samples.

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